

Another weighted approximation of functions with singularities by combinations of Bernstein operators

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Abstract

We give direct and converse results for the weighted approximation of functions with inner singularities by a new type of Bernstein operators.

Keywords: Combinations of modified Bernstein polynomials; Functions with singularities; Weighted approximation; Direct and inverse results.

1. Introduction

The present work continues to study modified Bernstein operators following [11]. Here, the notation is referred to [11], for convenience, these notations will be listed. The set of all continuous functions, defined on the interval I , is denoted by $C(I)$. For any $f \in C([0, 1])$, the corresponding Bernstein operators are defined as follows:

$$B_n(f, x) := \sum_{k=0}^n f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) p_{nk}(x),$$

where

$$p_{nk}(x) := \binom{n}{k} x^k (1-x)^{n-k}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad x \in [0, 1].$$

Let

$$\bar{w}(x) = |x - \xi|^\alpha, \quad 0 < \xi < 1, \quad \alpha > 0$$

and

$$C_{\bar{w}} := \{f \in C([0, 1] \setminus \xi) : \lim_{x \rightarrow \xi} (\bar{w}f)(x) = 0\}.$$

The norm $C_{\bar{w}}$ is defined as $\|f\|_{C_{\bar{w}}} := \|\bar{w}f\| = \sup_{0 \leq x \leq 1} |(\bar{w}f)(x)|$, and

$$W_{\bar{w}}^r := \{f \in C_{\bar{w}} : f^{(r-1)} \in A.C.((0,1)), \|\bar{w}\varphi^r f^{(r)}\| < \infty\}.$$

For $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, we define the weighted modulus of smoothness by

$$\omega_{\varphi}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}} := \sup_{0 < h \leq t} \{ \|\bar{w}\Delta_{h\varphi}^r f\|_{[16h^2, 1-16h^2]} + \|\bar{w}\vec{\Delta}_h^r f\|_{[0, 16h^2]} + \|\bar{w}\overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^r f\|_{[1-16h^2, 1]} \},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{h\varphi}^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x + (\frac{r}{2} - k)h\varphi(x)), \\ \vec{\Delta}_h^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x + (r - k)h), \\ \overleftarrow{\Delta}_h^r f(x) &= \sum_{k=0}^r (-1)^k \binom{r}{k} f(x - kh), \end{aligned}$$

and $\varphi(x) = \sqrt{x(1-x)}$. The weighted K -function is given by

$$K_{r,\varphi}(f, t^r)_{\bar{w}} := \inf_g \{ \|\bar{w}(f - g)\| + t^r \|\bar{w}\varphi^r g^{(r)}\| : g \in W_{\bar{w}}^r \}.$$

It was shown in [5] that $K_{\varphi}(f, t^r)_{\bar{w}} \sim \omega_{\varphi}^r(f, t)_{\bar{w}}$. Della Vecchia et al. firstly introduced $B_n^*(f, x)$ and $\bar{B}_n(f, x)$ in [3], where the properties of $B_n^*(f, x)$ and $\bar{B}_n(f, x)$ are studied.

Among others, they prove that

$$\begin{aligned} \|w(f - B_n^*(f))\| &\leq C\omega_{\varphi}^2(f, n^{-1/2}), \quad f \in C_w, \\ \|\bar{w}(f - \bar{B}_n(f))\| &\leq \frac{C}{n^{3/2}} \sum_{k=1}^{[\sqrt{n}]} k^2 \omega_{\varphi}^2(f, \frac{1}{k})_{\bar{w}}^*, \quad f \in C_{\bar{w}}, \end{aligned}$$

Where $w(x) = x^{\alpha}(1-x)^{\beta}$, $\alpha, \beta \geq 0$, $\alpha + \beta > 0$, $0 \leq x \leq 1$.

In [11], for any $\alpha, \beta > 0$, $n \geq 2r + \alpha + \beta$, there hold

$$\|wB_{n,r}^*(f)\| \leq C\|wf\|, \quad f \in C_w,$$

$$\|w(B_{n,r}^*(f) - f)\| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{C}{n^r}(\|wf\| + \|w\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), & f \in W_w^{2r}, \\ C(\omega_\varphi^{2r}(f, n^{-1/2})_w + n^{-r}\|wf\|), & f \in C_w, \end{cases}$$

$$\|w\varphi^{2r} B_{n,r}^{*(2r)}(f)\| \leq \begin{cases} Cn^r\|wf\|, & f \in C_w, \\ C(\|wf\| + \|w\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), & f \in W_w^{2r}. \end{cases}$$

and for any $0 < \gamma < 2r$,

$$\|w(B_{n,r}^*(f) - f)\| = O(n^{-\gamma/2}) \iff \omega_\varphi^{2r}(f, t)_w = O(t^\gamma).$$

The main purpose of the present paper is to give another new type of combinations of Bernstein operators so as to obtain higher approximation order. Throughout the paper, C denotes a positive constant independent of n and x , which may be different in different cases.

2. Main Results

For any positive integer r , we consider the determinant

$$A_r := \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ 2r+1 & 2r+2 & 2r+3 & \dots & 4r+1 \\ (2r)(2r+1) & (2r+1)(2r+2) & (2r+2)(2r+3) & \dots & (4r)(4r+1) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \ddots & \dots \\ 2 \dots (2r+1) & 3 \dots (2r+2) & 4 \dots (2r+3) & \dots & (2r+2) \dots (4r+1) \end{vmatrix}$$

We obtain $A_r = \prod_{j=2}^{2r} j!$. Thus, there is a unique solution for the system of nonhomogeneous linear equations:

$$\begin{cases} a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_{2r+1} = 1, \\ (2r+1)a_1 + (2r+2)a_2 + \dots + (4r+1)a_{2r+1} = 0, \\ (2r+1)(2r)a_1 + (2r+1)(2r+2)a_2 + \dots + (4r)(4r+1)a_{2r+1} = 0, \\ \vdots \\ (2r+1)!a_1 + 3 \dots (2r+2)a_2 + \dots + (2r+2) \dots (4r+1)a_{2r+1} = 0. \end{cases} \tag{2.1}$$

Let

$$\psi(x) = \begin{cases} a_1 x^{2r+1} + a_2 x^{2r+2} + \dots + a_{2r+1} x^{4r+1}, & 0 < x < 1, \\ 0, & x \leq 0, \\ 1, & x = 1. \end{cases}$$

with the coefficients $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{2r+1}$ satisfying (2.1). From (2.1), we see that $\psi(x) \in C^{(2r)}(-\infty, +\infty)$, $0 \leq \psi(x) \leq 1$ for $0 \leq x \leq 1$. Moreover, it holds that $\psi(1) = 1$, $\psi^{(i)}(0) = 0$, $i = 0, 1, \dots, 2r$. and $\psi^{(i)}(1) = 0$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 2r$.

Let

$$L_r(f, x) := \sum_{i=1}^{r+1} f(x_i)l_i(x),$$

Where

$$l_i(x) := \frac{\prod_{j=1, j \neq i}^{r+1} (x - x_j)}{\prod_{j=1, j \neq i}^{r+1} (x_i - x_j)},$$

$$x_i = \frac{[n\xi - ((r - 1)/2 + i)\sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r + 1.$$

and

$$R_r(f, x) := \sum_{i=1}^{r+1} f(x_i^*)l_i^*(x),$$

Where

$$l_i^*(x) := \frac{\prod_{j=1, j \neq i}^{r+1} (x - x_j^*)}{\prod_{j=1, j \neq i}^{r+1} (x_i^* - x_j^*)},$$

$$x_i^* = \frac{n - [n\xi - ((r - 1)/2 + i)\sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r + 1.$$

Further, let

$$x'_1 = \frac{[n\xi - 2\sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad x'_2 = \frac{[n\xi - \sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad x'_3 = \frac{[n\xi + \sqrt{n}]}{n}, \quad x'_4 = \frac{[n\xi + 2\sqrt{n}]}{n}.$$

Set

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{F}_n(f, x) &:= \bar{F}_n(x) = (1 - \psi(nx - 1))L_r(f, x) + (1 - \psi(nx - n + 2))\psi(nx - 1)f(x) \\ &\quad + \psi(nx - n + 2)R_r(f, x). \\ &= \begin{cases} L_r(f, x), & x \in [0, 1/n], \\ (1 - \psi(nx - 1))L_r(f, x) + \psi(nx - 1)f(x), & x \in [1/n, 2/n], \\ f(x), & x \in [2/n, 1 - 2/n], \\ (1 - \psi(nx - n + 2))f(x) + \psi(nx - n + 2)R_r(f, x), & x \in [1 - 2/n, 1 - 1/n], \\ R_r(f, x), & x \in [1 - 1/n, 1]. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

$\bar{F}_n(f, x)$ is a linear is a linear polynomial of degree r , and $\bar{F}_n(f, x) \in C^{(2r)}([0, 1])$, provided that $f \in C^{(2r)}([0, 1])$.

We define our combinations of Bernstein operators as follows:

$$\bar{B}_{n,r}(f, x) := B_{n,r}(\bar{F}_n, x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n)B_{n_i}(\bar{F}_n, x),$$

where $C_i(n)$ satisfy the conditions (a)-(d).

- (a) $n = n_0 < n_1 < \dots < n_{r-1} \leq Cn$,
- (b) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| \leq C$,
- (c) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n) = 1$,
- (d) $\sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n)n_i^{-k} = 0$, for $k = 1, \dots, r - 1$.

We have our main results as follows:

Theorem. For any $\alpha > 0$, $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, we have

$$\|\bar{w}\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f)\| \leq Cn^{2r}\|\bar{w}f\|, f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}, \tag{2.2}$$

$$|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f, x)| \leq \begin{cases} Cn^r \{\max\{n^{r(1-\lambda)}, \varphi^{2r(\lambda-1)}\}\}\|\bar{w}f\|, & f \in C_{\bar{w}}, \\ C(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda} f^{(2r)}\|), & f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}, \end{cases} \tag{2.3}$$

$$\|\bar{w}\bar{B}_{n,r}(f)\| \leq C\|\bar{w}f\|, f \in C_{\bar{w}}, \tag{2.4}$$

$$\|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - f)\| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{C}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), & f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}, \\ C(\omega_{\varphi}^{2r}(f, n^{-1/2})_{\bar{w}} + n^{-r}\|\bar{w}f\|), & f \in C_{\bar{w}}, \end{cases} \tag{2.5}$$

and for $0 < \gamma < 2r$,

$$\|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - f)\| = O(n^{-\gamma/2}) \iff \omega_{\varphi}^{2r}(f, t)_{\bar{w}} = O(t^r). \tag{2.6}$$

3. Lemmas

Lemma 1. ([13]) For any non-negative real u and v , we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^{-u} \left(1 - \frac{k}{n}\right)^{-v} p_{nk}(x) \leq Cx^{-u}(1-x)^{-v}. \tag{3.1}$$

Lemma 2. For any positive real α , and $f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}$, we have

$$\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r-2j} f^{(2r-j)}\| \leq C(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|). \tag{3.2}$$

Proof. It follows from Kolmogolov's inequality that

$$|f^{(2r-j)}(\frac{1}{2})| \leq C(\|f\|_{[1/4,3/4]} + \|f^{(2r)}\|_{[1/4,3/4]}),$$

Moreover,

$$|f^{(2r-j)}(\frac{1}{2})| \leq C(\|\bar{w}f\|_{[1/4,3/4]} + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|_{[1/4,3/4]}). \tag{3.3}$$

When $0 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2}$, if $|t - \xi| > \frac{1}{2\sqrt{n}}$, then $f^{(2r-j+1)}(t) \neq 0$. Moreover we have $\bar{w}(x) \leq \bar{w}(t)(1 + n^{\frac{\alpha}{2}}|t - x|)^{\alpha}$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} |(f^{(2r-j)}(x) - f^{(2r-j)}(\frac{1}{2}))| &\leq \int_x^{\frac{1}{2}} |f^{(2r-j+1)}(u)| du \\ &\leq C \frac{\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r-2j+2} f^{(2r-j+1)}\|}{\bar{w}(x)} \int_x^{\frac{1}{2}} \frac{\bar{w}(u) du}{\bar{w}(u)\varphi^{2r-2j+2}(u)} \\ &\leq C \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r-2j+2} f^{(2r-j+1)}\| \frac{x^{-r+j+1}(1 + n^{\frac{\alpha}{2}}x^{\alpha})}{\bar{w}(x)}. \end{aligned}$$

Which, together with (3.3), gives that

$$|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r-2j}(x)f^{(2r-j)}(x)| \leq C(\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r-2j+2} f^{(2r-j+1)}\| + \|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|).$$

Similarly, we can prove that the above inequality also holds when $\frac{1}{2} < x \leq 1$. Therefore we obtain that

$$|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r-2j}(x)f^{(2r-j)}(x)| \leq C(\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r-2j+2} f^{(2r-j+1)}\| + \|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|). \tag{3.4}$$

Now, the result follows from (3.4) when $j = 1$, and thus the result can be deduced from (3.4)

by induction when $1 < j \leq r$.

Lemma 3. $f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}, \alpha > 0$, we have

$$\|\bar{w}(f - L_r(f))\|_{[0, \frac{2}{n}]} \leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), \tag{3.5}$$

$$\|\bar{w}(f - R_r(f))\|_{[1-\frac{2}{n}, 1]} \leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|). \tag{3.6}$$

The proof is similar to the lemma 3 of [?], we don't give a proof here.

Lemma 4. For any $f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}$ and $\alpha > 0$, we have

$$\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} \bar{F}_n^{(2r)}\| \leq C(\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\| + \|\bar{w}f\|). \tag{3.7}$$

The proof is similar to the lemma 4 of [11], we don't give a proof here.

Lemma 5. ([3]) Let $A_n(x) := \bar{w}(x) \sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} p_{n,k}(x)$. Then $A_n(x) \leq Cn^{-\alpha/2}$ for $0 < \xi < 1$ and $\alpha > 0$.

Lemma 6. For $0 < \xi < 1, \alpha, \beta > 0$, we have

$$\bar{w}(x) \sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} |k-nx|^\beta p_{n,k}(x) \leq C n^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{2}} \varphi^\beta(x). \tag{3.8}$$

Proof. By (3.1) and the lemma 5, we have

$$\bar{w}(x)^{\frac{1}{2n}} (\bar{w}(x) \sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} p_{n,k}(x))^{\frac{2n-1}{2n}} \left(\sum_{|k-n\xi| \leq \sqrt{n}} |k-nx|^{2n\beta} p_{n,k}(x) \right)^{\frac{1}{2n}} \leq C n^{\frac{\beta-\alpha}{2}} \varphi^\beta(x).$$

4 Proof of Theorem 1

4.1 Proof of (2.2)

We first prove $x \in [0, \frac{1}{n}]$ (The same as $x \in [1 - \frac{1}{n}, 1]$), now

$$\begin{aligned} |\bar{w}(x) \bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f, x)| &\leq \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \frac{n_i!}{(n_i - 2r)!} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-2r} |C_i(n) \bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r} \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\ &\leq C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} n_i^{2r} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-2r} |C_i(n) \bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r} \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\ &\leq C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} n_i^{2r} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-2r} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} C_{2r}^j |C_i(n) \bar{F}_n(\frac{k+2r-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\ &\leq C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} n_i^{2r} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} C_{2r}^j |C_i(n) \bar{F}_n(\frac{2r-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-2r,0}(x) \\ &\quad + C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} n_i^{2r} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} C_{2r}^j |C_i(n) \bar{F}_n(\frac{n_i-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-2r,n_i-2r}(x) \\ &\quad + C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} n_i^{2r} \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-2r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} C_{2r}^j |C_i(n) \bar{F}_n(\frac{k+2r-j}{n_i})| p_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\ &:= H_1 + H_2 + H_3. \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_1 &\leq C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} n_i^{2r} \left(\sum_{j=0}^{2r-1} |C_i(n)\bar{F}_n(\frac{2r-j}{n_i})| + |\bar{F}_n(0)| \right) p_{n_i-2r,0}(x) \\
 &\leq Cn^{2r} \|\bar{w}f\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r-1} \left(\frac{n_i|x-\xi|}{2r-j-n_i\xi} \right)^\alpha (1-x)^{n_i-2r} \\
 &\leq Cn^{2r} \|\bar{w}f\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} (n_i|x-\xi|)^\alpha (1-x)^{n_i-2r} \\
 &\leq Cn^{2r} \|\bar{w}f\|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can get $H_2 \leq Cn^{2r} \|\bar{w}f\|$ and $H_3 \leq Cn^{2r} \|\bar{w}f\|$.

When $x \in [\frac{1}{n}, 1 - \frac{1}{n}]$, according to [5], we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|\bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f, x)| \\
 = &|\bar{w}(x)B_{n,r}^{(2r)}(\bar{F}_n, x)| \\
 = &\bar{w}(x)(\varphi^2(x))^{-2r} \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} |Q_j(x, n_i)C_i(n)| n_i^j \sum_{k/n_i \in A} \left| \left(x - \frac{k}{n_i}\right)^j \bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right) \right| p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 &+ \bar{w}(x)(\varphi^2(x))^{-2r} \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} |Q_j(x, n_i)C_i(n)| n_i^j \sum_{x'_2 \leq k/n_i \leq x'_3} \left| \left(x - \frac{k}{n_i}\right)^j H\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right) \right| p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 := &\sigma_1 + \sigma_2. \tag{4.2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $A := [0, x'_2] \cup [x'_3, 1]$, H is a linear function. If $\frac{k}{n_i} \in A$, when $\frac{\bar{w}(x)}{\bar{w}(\frac{k}{n_i})} \leq C(1 + n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}} |k - n_i x|^\alpha)$, we have $|k - n_i \xi| \geq \frac{\sqrt{n_i}}{2}$, then

$$Q_j(x, n_i) = (n_i x(1-x))^{[(2r-j)/2]}, \text{ and } (\varphi^2(x))^{-2r} Q_j(x, n_i) n_i^j \leq C(n_i/\varphi^2(x))^{r+j/2}.$$

By (3.8), then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_1 &\leq C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} |C_i(n)| \left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{r+j/2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} \left| \left(x - \frac{k}{n_i}\right)^j \bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right) \right| p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 &\leq C\|\bar{w}f\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} |C_i(n)| \left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{r+j/2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} [1 + n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}} |k - n_i x|^\alpha] \left|x - \frac{k}{n_i}\right|^j p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 := &I_1 + I_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

By a simple calculation, we have $I_1 \leq Cn^{2r} \|\bar{w}f\|$. By (3.1), then

$$I_2 \leq C \|\bar{w}f\| \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} |C_i(n)| n_i^{-(\frac{\alpha}{2}+j)} \left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{j/2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |k - n_i x|^{\alpha+j} p_{n_i,k}(x) \leq Cn^{2r} \|\bar{w}f\|.$$

We note $|H(\frac{k}{n_i})| \leq \max(|H(x'_1)|, |H(x'_4)|) := H(a)$.

If $x \in [x'_1, x'_4]$, we have $\bar{w}(x) \leq \bar{w}(a)$.

$$\sigma_2 \leq C\bar{w}(a)H(a)n^r \varphi^{-2r}(x) \leq Cn^{2r} \|\bar{w}f\|.$$

If $x \notin [x'_1, x'_4]$, then $\bar{w}(a) > n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}$ we have

$$\sigma_2 \leq C\bar{w}(a)H(a)\varphi^{-2r}(x)\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n)n_i^{r+\frac{\alpha}{2}} \sum_{x'_2 \leq k/n_i \leq x'_3} p_{n_i,k}(x) \leq Cn^{2r} \|\bar{w}f\|.$$

It follows from combining the above inequalities (4.1) and (4.2) that the theorem is proved.

4.2 Proof of (2.3)

(1) When $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, we discuss it as follows:

Case 1. If $0 \leq \varphi(x) \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, by (2.2), we have

$$|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f, x)| \leq Cn^{-r\lambda} |\bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f, x)| \leq Cn^{r(2-\lambda)} \|\bar{w}f\|. \tag{4.3}$$

Case2. If $\varphi(x) > \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & |\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f, x)| = |B_{n,r}^{(2r)}(\bar{F}_n, x)| \\ & \leq (\varphi^2(x))^{-2r} \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} |Q_j(x, n_i)C_i(n)| n_i^j \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |(x - \frac{k}{n_i})^j \bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})| p_{n_i,k}(x), \end{aligned}$$

$Q_j(x, n_i) = (n_i x(1-x))^{[(2r-j)/2]}$, and $(\varphi^2(x))^{-2r} Q_j(x, n_i) n_i^j \leq C(n_i/\varphi^2(x))^{r+j/2}$. So

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f, x)| \\
 & \leq C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} |C_i(n)| \left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{r+j/2} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} \left|(x - \frac{k}{n_i}\right)^j \bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right)| p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 & = C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} |C_i(n)| \left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{r+j/2} \sum_{k/n_i \in A} \left|(x - \frac{k}{n_i}\right)^j \bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right)| p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 & \quad + C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{j=0}^{2r} |C_i(n)| \left(\frac{n_i}{\varphi^2(x)}\right)^{r+j/2} \sum_{x'_2 \leq k/n_i \leq x'_3} \left|(x - \frac{k}{n_i}\right)^j \bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right)| p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 & := \sigma_1 + \sigma_2.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.4}$$

Where $A := [0, x'_2] \cup [x'_3, 1]$. We can easily get $\sigma_1 \leq n^r \varphi^{2r(\lambda-1)}(x) \|\bar{w}f\|$, $\sigma_2 \leq n^r \varphi^{2r(\lambda-1)}(x) \|\bar{w}f\|$. By bringing these facts (4.3) and (4.4) together, the theorem is proved.

2) When $f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}$, we have

$$B_{n,r}^{(2r)}(\bar{F}_n, x) = \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} C_i(n) n_i^{2r} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i-2r} \overrightarrow{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r} \bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right) p_{n_i-2r,k}(x).
 \tag{4.5}$$

If $0 < k < n_i - 2r$, we have

$$\left| \overrightarrow{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r} \bar{F}_n\left(\frac{k}{n_i}\right) \right| \leq C n_i^{-2r+1} \int_0^{\frac{2r}{n_i}} |\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}\left(\frac{k}{n_i} + u\right)| du,
 \tag{4.6}$$

If $k = 0$, we have

$$\left| \overrightarrow{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r} \bar{F}_n(0) \right| \leq C n_i^{-r+1} \int_0^{\frac{2r}{n_i}} u^{2r-1} |\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(u)| du,
 \tag{4.7}$$

Similarly

$$\left| \overrightarrow{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r} \bar{F}_n\left(\frac{n_i - 2r}{n_i}\right) \right| \leq C n_i^{-2r+1} \int_{1-\frac{2r}{n_i}}^1 (1-u)^{2r-1} |\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(u)| du.$$

By (4.5) and (4.6), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f,x)| &\leq C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i^{2r}\sum_{k=0}^{n_i-2r}|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r}\bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})|p_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\
 &= C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i^{2r}\sum_{k=1}^{n_i-2r-1}|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r}\bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})|p_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\
 &\quad +C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i^{2r}|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r}\bar{F}_n(0)|p_{n_i-2r,0}(x) \\
 &\quad +C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i^{2r}|\bar{\Delta}_{\frac{1}{n_i}}^{2r}\bar{F}_n(\frac{n_i-2r}{n_i})|p_{n_i-2r,n_i-2r}(x) \\
 &:= I_1 + I_2 + I_3.
 \end{aligned}$$

By (4.6), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1 &\leq C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i\sum_{k=1}^{n_i-2r-1}\int_0^{\frac{2r}{n_i}}|\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(\frac{k}{n_i}+u)|dup_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\
 &= C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i\sum_{k/n_i\in A}\int_0^{\frac{2r}{n_i}}|\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(\frac{k}{n_i}+u)|dup_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\
 &\quad +C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i\sum_{x'_2\leq k/n_i\leq x'_3}\int_0^{\frac{2r}{n_i}}|H_n^{(2r)}(\frac{k}{n_i}+u)|dup_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\
 &:= T_1 + T_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $A := [0, x'_2] \cup [x'_3, 1]$, H is a linear function. If $\frac{k}{n_i} \in A$, when $\frac{\bar{w}(x)}{\bar{w}(\frac{k}{n_i})} \leq C(1 + n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}|k - n_i x|^\alpha)$, we have $|k - n_i \xi| \geq \frac{\sqrt{n_i}}{2}$, by (3.1) and (3.7), then

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_1 &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}F^{(2r)}\|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i\sum_{k/n_i\in A}\int_0^{\frac{2r}{n_i}}\bar{w}^{-1}(\frac{k}{n_i}+u)\varphi^{-2r\lambda}(\frac{k}{n_i}+u)dup_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\
 &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}F^{(2r)}\|\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i\sum_{k=0}^{n_i}\int_0^{\frac{2r}{n_i}}[1 + n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}|k - n_i x|^\alpha]\varphi^{-2r\lambda}(\frac{k}{n_i})dup_{n_i-2r,k}(x) \\
 &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}\| \leq C(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}f^{(2r)}\|).
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can get $T_2 \leq C(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}f^{(2r)}\|)$. So $I_1 \leq C(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}f^{(2r)}\|)$ and by (4.7), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2 &\leq C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i^{2r}|\bar{\Delta}_{n_i}^{2r}\bar{F}_n(0)|p_{n_i-2r,0}(x) \\
 &\leq C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r\lambda}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|n_i^{r+1}\int_0^{\frac{2r}{n_i}}u^{2r-1}|\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(u)|dun_i^{-2r,0}(x) \\
 &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}\|\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}(n_i x)^{r(1+\lambda)}(1-x)^{r\lambda}\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}\| \\
 &\leq C(\|\bar{w}f\|+\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}f^{(2r)}\|).
 \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, $I_3 \leq C(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r\lambda}f^{(2r)}\|)$, then the theorem is proved.

Corollary 1. If $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda = 0$, we have

$$|\bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f, x)| \leq \begin{cases} Cn^{2r}\|\bar{w}f\|, & f \in C_{\bar{w}}, \\ C(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}f^{(2r)}\|), & f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 2. If $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda = 1$, we have

$$|\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f, x)| \leq \begin{cases} Cn^r\|\bar{w}f\|, & f \in C_{\bar{w}}, \\ C(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r}f^{(2r)}\|), & f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}. \end{cases}$$

4.3 Proof of (2.4)

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\bar{w}(x)\bar{B}_{n,r}(f, x)| &= |\bar{w}(x)B_{n,r}(\bar{F}_n, x)| \leq \bar{w}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}\sum_{k=1}^{n_i-1}|C_i(n)\bar{F}_n(\frac{k}{n_i})|p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 &\quad + \bar{w}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)\bar{F}_n(0)|p_{n_i,0}(x) + \bar{w}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)\bar{F}_n(1)|p_{n_i,n_i}(x) \\
 &:= I_1 + I_2 + I_3.
 \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, the theorem can be proved easily.

4.4. Proof of (2.5)

We assume $f \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}$, then $\|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - \bar{F}_n)\| \leq \frac{C}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r}f^{(2r)}\|)$.

Recall that [?], then

$$B_{n,r}((t-x)^j, x) = 0, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r, \tag{4.8}$$

$$B_{n,r}((t-x)^{2r-j}, x) = O(n^{-r}\varphi^{2r-2j}(x)), \quad x \in [\frac{1}{n}, 1 - \frac{1}{n}], \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, r. \tag{4.9}$$

Case 1. $x \in [\frac{1}{n}, 1 - \frac{1}{n}]$. By using Taylor expansion, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \bar{w}(x)(\bar{F}_n(x) - B_{n,r}(\bar{F}_n, x)) \\ = & \bar{w}(x) \sum_{j=1}^{2r-1} \frac{1}{(2r-j)!} B_{n,r}((t-x)^{2r-j}, x) \bar{F}_n^{(2r-j)}(x) \\ & + \bar{w}(x) B_{n,r}(\frac{1}{(2r-j)!} \int_x^t (t-u)^{2r-1} \bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(u) du, x) \\ := & I_1 + I_2. \end{aligned}$$

By (3.2), (3.7) and (4.9), we have $1 \leq j \leq r$, then

$$\frac{\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{2r-2j}(x)}{n^r} \bar{F}_n^{(2r-j)}(x) \leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}\bar{F}_n\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} \bar{F}_n^{(2r)}\|) \leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), \quad (4.10)$$

By (4.8) and (4.10), we have

$$I_1 \leq \bar{w}(x) \sum_{j=1}^{r-1} \frac{1}{(2r-j)!} |B_{n,r}((t-x)^{2r-j}, x) \bar{F}_n^{(2r-j)}(x)| \leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|).$$

If u is between t and x we have $\frac{|u-x|^{2r-1}}{\varphi^{2r}(u)} \leq \frac{|t-x|^{2r-1}}{\varphi^{2r}(t)}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & |\bar{w}(x) B_{n,r}(\frac{1}{(2r-j)!} \int_x^t (t-u)^{2r-1} \bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(u) du, x)| \\ \leq & C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} |C_i(n)| \int_x^{\frac{k}{n_i}} |(\frac{k}{n_i} - u)^{2r-1} \bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(u)| du p_{n_i,k}(x) \\ = & C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-1} |C_i(n)| \int_x^{\frac{k}{n_i}} |(\frac{k}{n_i} - u)^{2r-1} \bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(u)| du p_{n_i,k}(x) \\ & + C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| (1-x)^{n_i} \int_0^x u^{2r-1} |\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(u)| du \\ & + C \bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| x^{n_i} \int_x^1 (1-u)^{2r-1} |\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(u)| du \\ := & J_1 + J_2 + J_3. \end{aligned}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_1 &\leq C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{-2r}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}\sum_{k/n_i\in A}|C_i(n)\left(\frac{k}{n_i}-x\right)^{2r-1}|\int_x^{\frac{k}{n_i}}\varphi^{2r}(v)|\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}(v)|dv p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 &\quad +C\bar{w}(x)\varphi^{-2r}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}\sum_{x'_2\leq k/n_i\leq x'_3}|C_i(n)\left(\frac{k}{n_i}-x\right)^{2r-1}|\int_x^{\frac{k}{n_i}}\varphi^{2r}(v)|H^{(2r)}(v)|dv p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 &:= \sigma_1 + \sigma_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, we can get $\sigma_1 \leq \frac{C}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r}f^{(2r)}\|)$. We note that $|\varphi^{2r}(v)H^{(2r)}(v)| \leq \max(|\varphi^{2r}(x'_1)H^{(2r)}(x'_1)|, |\varphi^{2r}(x'_4)H^{(2r)}(x'_4)|) := |\varphi^{2r}(a)H^{(2r)}(a)|$, $H^{(2r)}(x)$ is a linear function.

If $x \in [x'_1, x'_4]$, then $\bar{w}(x) \leq \bar{w}(a)$. So we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_2 &\leq C\bar{w}(a)\varphi^{2r}(a)|H^{(2r)}(a)|\varphi^{-2r}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}\sum_{k=1}^{n_i-1}|C_i(n)|\left(\frac{k}{n_i}-x\right)^{2r}p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 &\leq \frac{C}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r}f^{(2r)}\|),
 \end{aligned}$$

If $x \notin [x'_1, x'_4]$, by $\bar{w}(a) > n_i^{-\frac{\alpha}{2}}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_2 &\leq C\bar{w}(a)\varphi^{-2r}(a)|H^{(2r)}(a)|\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}\sum_{x'_2\leq k/n_i\leq x'_3}n_i^{\frac{\alpha}{2}}|C_i(n)|\left(\frac{k}{n_i}-x\right)^{2r}p_{n_i,k}(x) \\
 &\leq \frac{C}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r}f^{(2r)}\|).
 \end{aligned}$$

For J_2 , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_2 &\leq C\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r}\bar{F}_n^{(2r)}\|\bar{w}(x)\sum_{i=0}^{r-1}|C_i(n)|(1-x)^{n_i}\int_0^x u^{2r-1}\bar{w}^{-1}(u)\varphi^{-2r}(u)du \\
 &\leq \frac{C}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r}f^{(2r)}\|).
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have

$$J_3 \leq \frac{C}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r}f^{(2r)}\|).$$

By bringing these facts together, we have

$$\|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - \bar{F}_n)\| \leq \frac{C}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r}f^{(2r)}\|).$$

Case 2. $x \in [0, \frac{1}{n}]$ (Similarly as $x \in [1 - \frac{1}{n}, 1]$). By using Taylor expansion, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{w}(x)|B_{n,r}(\bar{F}_n, x) - \bar{F}_n(x)| &\leq \frac{\bar{w}(x)}{r!} \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| B_{n_i} \left(\int_x^t |(t-u)^r \bar{F}_n^{(r+1)}(u)| du, x \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{\bar{w}(x)}{r!} \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| (1-x)^{n_i} \int_0^x u^{2r-1} |\bar{F}_n^{(r+1)}(u)| du \\ &:= J_1 + J_2. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} J_1 &\leq C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{k=0}^{n_i} \int_x^{\frac{k}{n_i}} |C_i(n)| \left(\frac{k}{n_i} - u\right)^r |\bar{F}_n^{(r+1)}(u)| du p_{n_i, k}(x) \\ &:= C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_i-1} \int_x^{\frac{k}{n_i}} |C_i(n)| \left(\frac{k}{n_i} - u\right)^r |\bar{F}_n^{(r+1)}(u)| du p_{n_i, k}(x) \\ &\quad + C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| x^{n_i} \int_x^1 (1-u)^r |\bar{F}_n^{(r+1)}(u)| du \\ &\quad + C\bar{w}(x) \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} |C_i(n)| (1-x)^{n_i} \int_0^x u^r |\bar{F}_n^{(r+1)}(u)| du \\ &:= I_1 + I_2 + I_3. \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, we can get

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &\leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), \\ I_2 &\leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), \\ I_3 &\leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|). \\ J_1 &\leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|), \\ J_2 &\leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|). \end{aligned} \tag{4.11}$$

So, we have

$$\|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - \bar{F}_n)\| \leq \frac{C}{n^r} (\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - f)\| &\leq \|\bar{w}(f - \bar{F}_n(f))\| + \|\bar{w}(\bar{F}_n(f) - \bar{B}_{n,r}(f))\| \\ &\leq \frac{C}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}f\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} f^{(2r)}\|). \end{aligned}$$

If $f \in C_{\bar{w}}$, there exists $g \in W_{\bar{w}}^{2r}$, by (2.4) and the first inequality of (2.5), then

$$\begin{aligned} \|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - f)\| &\leq \|\bar{w}(f - g)\| + \|\bar{w}\bar{B}_{n,r}(f - g)\| + \|\bar{w}(g - \bar{B}_{n,r}(g))\| \\ &\leq C(\|\bar{w}(f - g)\| + \frac{1}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}g\| + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} g^{(2r)}\|)) \\ &\leq C(\omega_{\varphi}^{2r}(f, n^{-1/2})_{\bar{w}} + n^{-r}\|\bar{w}f\|). \end{aligned}$$

4.5. Proof of (2.6)

From the proof of (2.5), we actually have

$$\|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - f)\| \leq CK_{2r,\varphi}(f, t^r)_{\bar{w}}.$$

Therefore, $K_{2r,\varphi}(f, n^{-r})_{\bar{w}} = O(t^\alpha)$ implies

$$\|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - f)\| \leq (n^{-\alpha/2}).$$

By (2.3) and (2.4), we may choose g properly such that $\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} g^{(2r)}\| < \infty$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_{\varphi}^{2r}(f, n^{-1/2})_{\bar{w}} + \frac{\|\bar{w}f\|}{n^r} &\leq \|\bar{w}(\bar{B}_{n,r}(f) - f)\| + \frac{1}{n^r}(\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} \bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(f - g)\| \\ &\quad + \|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} \bar{B}_{n,r}^{(2r)}(g)\|) + \frac{\|\bar{w}f\|}{n^r} \\ &\leq \|\bar{w}(f - \bar{B}_{n,r}(f))\| + \frac{\|\bar{w}f\|}{n^r} + C\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^r(\|\bar{w}(f - g)\| \\ &\quad + k^{-r}\|\bar{w}\varphi^{2r} g^{(2r)}\| + k^{-r}\|\bar{w}f\|) \\ &\leq \|\bar{w}(f - \bar{B}_{n,r}(f))\| + C\left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^r(\omega_{\varphi}^{2r}(f, k^{-1/2})_{\bar{w}} \\ &\quad + k^{-r}\|\bar{w}f\|). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by [5], we obtain the converse inequality.

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